

Figure S1: Phylogeny of Testudine genomes available on NCBI (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/assembly/search=Turtle>) made with Timetree (see Methods). Species in bold text contain hAT-6_XT DNA transposable element.

Etheostoma_spectabile -----MAK-----RKMYSERIFQSRWENEYMFTEIAGKLVCLCGSNVAVMKE
Malaclemys_terrapi_n_terrapi_n -----
Trachemys_scripta_elegans -----MAK-----RKIDSENRGFQSRWENEYMFTEIAGKPVCLCGSNIAVMKE
Scophthalmus_maximus -----MAK-----RKVDSENRRAFQNRWEAEYMFTEIAGKPVCLVCGANVAVIKE
Syngnathus_acus -----MPK-----RKVDSENRRAFKNRWEVEYMFTEIAGKPVCLICGANVAVLKE
Thalassophryne_amazonica -----MPK-----RKVDSENRRAFKSRWEAEYMFTEIAGKPVCLICGDNVAVIKE
Xenopus_tropicalis -----MPK-----RKVDSKNRAFKNRWEAEYMFTEIAGKPLCLICGANVAVIKE
Scleropages_formosus MLQVIAKLALTMPK-----RKVDSENRRAFKNRWEAEYMFTEIAGKPVCLICGANVAVIKE

Etheostoma_spectabile YNLRHHYETKHEDKLNLSAGQKLQKVEELKKNLTSQQTFFTKAKSQSEAAVKASFIVAE
Malaclemys_terrapi_n_terrapi_n -----
Trachemys_scripta_elegans YNLRHHYETKHENKFNLSAGQKLQKVEELKKNLTSQQTFFTKAKSQSEAAVKASFIVAE
Scophthalmus_maximus FNIRRHYETKHQE-LQNLNAEKKIQRVKELKKNLRFQQTFFTRAKSQSEAAVKASFIVAQ
Syngnathus_acus FNLRHHYETKHLNLDLNAEQKIQKVEELKKNLTFQQTFFTRAKSQSEAAVKASFIVAE
Thalassophryne_amazonica FNLRHHCETKHQDNLKDLNAEQKIQAEDLKKNLTLQQTFFTRAKSQSEAAVKSSFIAAE
Xenopus_tropicalis FNLRHHYETKHQDNLKDLNAEQKIQKVEELKKNLTLQQTIFTRAKSESEAAVKASFIVAE
Scleropages_formosus FDLRRHYETKHQDNLKDLNAEQKIQAEEELKKNLTLQQMFFTRAKSQSEAAVKASFIVAE

Etheostoma_spectabile EIAKSGRPFTEGEFVKNCMMKVCDVCPDKTRAFANVLSRNTVANRVCEMATDLKTQLI
Malaclemys_terrapi_n_terrapi_n -----MATDLKTQLI
Trachemys_scripta_elegans EIAKSGRPFTEGEFVKNCMMKVCDVCPDKTRAFANVLSRNTVANRVCEMATDLKTQLI
Scophthalmus_maximus EIAKSARPFTEGEFLKSCMMKVCDVCPENKQMFANVLSRNTVADRICEMATDLKTQLS
Syngnathus_acus EIAKAGRPFTEGEFLKSCMVKCDIICPDKKQMLANVLSRNTVADRICEMATDLRTQLS
Thalassophryne_amazonica EIAKSARPFTEGEFLKSCMIKVFVLCVDPKQILANVLSRKMIAADRICEMATDLRTQLS
Xenopus_tropicalis EIAKSARPFTEGEFLKSCMIKVFVLCVDPKQMLAN-----
Scleropages_formosus EVAKSARPFTEGEFLKSCMIKVFVLCVDPKQMLANVLSRNTIADRIVREMATDLRTQLS

Etheostoma_spectabile ERAKDFVAYSLAVDETTDSTAQLAIFIRGVDSNLCVTEEILDIKSMHGTTKGEDIFGN
Malaclemys_terrapi_n_terrapi_n ERAKDFVAYSLAVDETTDATDAQLAIFIRGVDSNLCVTQEILDIKSMHGTTKGEDIFGN
Trachemys_scripta_elegans ERAKDFVAYSLAVDETTDATDAQLAIFIRGVDSNLCVTEEILDIKSMHGTTKGEDIFGN
Scophthalmus_maximus ERSKDFATFASLAVDESTDMTDAQLAIFIREVDSSLCVTEEILDIKSMHGTTGKDFIFEN
Syngnathus_acus KRKDFIAYSLAMDESTDMTDAELAIFIRGVDSLVRT-----FEN
Thalassophryne_amazonica ERSKDFIAYSLAVDESTDMTDAQLAIFIRGVDSNLRVTEEIMDIKLMHGTTGKDFIFEN
Xenopus_tropicalis -----
Scleropages_formosus ERSKDFIAYSLAVDESTDMTDAQLAIFIRGVDSNLRVTEEIMDIKLMHGTTGKDFIFEN

*

Etheostoma_spectabile VFQSVTDMRLPWEKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGEKKWTGGKDALKDAGGELCR-----
Malaclemys_terrapi_n_terrapi_n VFQSVTDMKLPWEKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGEKNLGVGRMRKMRRE-ENCA-----
Trachemys_scripta_elegans VFQSVTDMKLPWEKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGEKNLGVGRMRKMRRE-ENCAGELTVYHCIIHQ
Scophthalmus_maximus VCQSITDMKLPWDKLVGLTTDGAPAMCSEKVLVGRMRAKMQE-ENCTGELTAYHCIIHQ
Syngnathus_acus VCQSVTDMKLPWDKLVGLTTDGAPAMCGEKNLGVGRMRKMRRE-ENCTGELTTYHCIIHQ
Thalassophryne_amazonica VCQSITDMKLPWDKRIALTTDGAPSMCSEKRVLVGRMRVKMQE--ENCT-----
Xenopus_tropicalis -----
Scleropages_formosus VCQSITDMKLPWDKLVGLTTDGAPSMCSEKVLVGRMRVKMQE-ENCTGELTAYHCIIHQ

*

Etheostoma_spectabile -----AHGLNHRQFQSFLEIDCEFGDMPYHTEVRWLSRG
Malaclemys_terrapi_n_terrapi_n -----EPRLNHRQFQSFLEIDSEFGDMPYHTEVRWLSRG
Trachemys_scripta_elegans ESLSAKVLKMDHVMNTVTQTVNFIRAHGLNHRQFQSFLEIDSEFGDMPYHTEVRWLSRG
Scophthalmus_maximus EMLCCKVLKMEHVMNTVTQTVNFIRAKGLNHWQFQSFMRREIDSEFADIPYHTEVRWLSRG
Syngnathus_acus EALCGKVLKMDHVMNTVTQTVNFIRSRGLNHRQFQSFMRRTIDSEFADIPYHTEVRWLSRG
Thalassophryne_amazonica -----EVRWLSWG

Xenopus_tropicalis	-----
Scleropages_formosus	EALCGKVLKMDNVMLSTLTQTVNFIRAKGLNHRQFQSFMRIDESEFADIPYHTEVRWLSRG
	**
Etheostoma_spectabile	KVLKRHFELREEICQFMDSKGDCTVLRDEKWKCELAFLADITSHLSALNLQLQGREHII
Malaclemys_terrapiin_terrapiin	KVLKRHFELREEICQFMDSKGDCTVLRDEKWKCELVFLADITSHLSALNLQLQGREHII
Trachemys_scripta_elegans	KVLKRHFELREEICQFMDSKGDCTVLRDEKWKCELAFLADITSHLSALNLQLQGREHII
Scophthalmus_maximus	KVLNRVFELSKEICQFMDSKGDCTVLRDEKWKCELAFLADVTAHLNVLNLHLQGRDRII
Syngnathus_acus	KVLNRVFELSNEICQFMDSKGDSTVLRDEKWKCELAFLADITAHLNALNLQLQGRDRMI
Thalassophryne_amazonica	KVLSRVFELSNIKICQFMDSKGDSTNFRDEKWKCKLAFLADITAHLNALNLQLQGRDRMI
Xenopus_tropicalis	-----
Scleropages_formosus	KVLDRVFELSNEICQFIDSKGKDSTNFRDEKWKCELAFLADITAHLNALNLQLQGRDRMI
Etheostoma_spectabile	TDMHDAVKAFQVKLRLLWETQMHQCNSLPHFCCQVILNQESDVFVPNATFAEKLARSARTEF
Malaclemys_terrapiin_terrapiin	TDMHDAVKAFQVKLRLLWETHMHQCNSLPHFCCQVIRNQESATVFPNATFAEKLARSARTEF
Trachemys_scripta_elegans	TDMHDAVKAFQVKLRLLWETQMHQCNSLPHFCCQVIRNQESATVFPNATFAEKLARSARTEF
Scophthalmus_maximus	TDMYDVTVKAFVKLLWETQMRQSNLPHFCCQVMFNQVGVATVFPNTHFADKLSARTEF
Syngnathus_acus	TDMYDAVKAFQVKLILWETQMLQCNSLPHFCCQVMLNQVGTTFVFNTHFAVKLSARTEF
Thalassophryne_amazonica	TDMYDAVKAFQVKLLWESQMHQCNSHSPCCQVMLNQAGTTVFPNMHFADKLSARTEF
Xenopus_tropicalis	-----
Scleropages_formosus	TDMYDAVKAFQVKLLWETQMRQCNSLPHFCCQVMLNQVGTTFVFNTHFADKLSARTEF
Etheostoma_spectabile	ARRFSDFEAQKSNFELLRNPFVAVDVETAPVEMQMELIELQCNGTLKAKYDTEGPAQFTRF
Malaclemys_terrapiin_terrapiin	ARRFSDFEAQKSNFELLRNPFVAVDVETAPVEMQMELIELQCNGTLKAKYDTAGPAQFTRF
Trachemys_scripta_elegans	ARRFSDFEAQKSNFELLRNPFVAVDVETAPVEMQMELIELQCNGTLKAKYDTAGPAQFTRF
Scophthalmus_maximus	ARRFGDF-----RNPFAVDVETAPVQIQMELIELQCNGTLKAKYDTAGPAQFIRS
Syngnathus_acus	ARRFGDFEEQKNFELFRNPFVAVDESAPVQIQMELIELQCNGTLKSKYDTAGPTEFIHS
Thalassophryne_amazonica	ARRFGDFEEQKNLELLRNPFVAVDVETAPVQIQMELIELQCNGTLKAKYDTAGPPQFIHA
Xenopus_tropicalis	-----IQMELIELQCNGTLKAKYDTAGPAQFIHS
Scleropages_formosus	ARRFGDFEEQKNFELRNPFVAVDVETAPVQIQMELIELQCNGTLKAKYDTAGPAQFIHS
Etheostoma_spectabile	L--PEAMPQLRQHAARILSMFGSTYSGAQKFTYTCLS-----
Malaclemys_terrapiin_terrapiin	I--PEAMQQLRQHAARILSMFGSTYLCEQLFVSMKINKTSHRSRLTDEHLQSILRIFTTQ
Trachemys_scripta_elegans	I--PEAMPQLRQHAARILSMFGSTYLCEQLFVSMKINKTSHRSRLTDEHLQSILRIFTTQ
Scophthalmus_maximus	I--PETMPQLRLHAAQTLCMFGSTYLCEKLFVSMKMNKTAHRSRLTDGHLQSILRISTAQ
Syngnathus_acus	I--PAAMSQRLRHVARTLCMFGSTYLCEKLFVSMKTNKTAHRSRLTDEHLQSILRVSTTR
Thalassophryne_amazonica	I--PAEMPQLRLHVARTLCMFGSTYLCEKLFVSMKTNKTAHRSRLTDEHLQSILRISTTQ
Xenopus_tropicalis	I--PAEMPQLRLHAARTLCMFGSTYLCEKLLSVMKTNKTAHRRHLTDEHLQSILRIS-TQ
Scleropages_formosus	I--PAEMPQLRLHAARTLCMFGSTYLCEKLFVSMKTNKTAHGSRLTDEHLQSILRISTTQ
	*
Etheostoma_spectabile	-----
Malaclemys_terrapiin_terrapiin	NLTPNINELVAKKRLQVSGSD---
Trachemys_scripta_elegans	NLTPNINELVAKKRLQVSGSD---
Scophthalmus_maximus	ELTPNLNDLTAKKRCQTSKSDKMA
Syngnathus_acus	DLTPNINQLVAKKRCQSSGSDKMA
Thalassophryne_amazonica	KLTPNIKELVAKKRCQASSFDKTT
Xenopus_tropicalis	NLTPNINLNFV---CQASSDKMT
Scleropages_formosus	NLTPNINELVAKKRCQASSDKMT

Figure S2: Conservation of the DDE catalytic triad in hAT-6_XT transposases marked by asterisk (*).

Figure S3: Predicted 3D structure of hAT-6_XTs and the essential residues required for transposition.

(1) The predicted 3D structures of a sample of hAT_XT transposases. 1.A) Three-dimensional ribbon structure of the Hermes DNA transposase monomer (<https://www.rcsb.org/structure/2BW3>). AlphaFold structural alignment of the best-predicted ribbon structures of 1.B) hAT-6_XT_TSE 1.C) hAT-6_XT_SFo, and 1.D) hAT-6_XT_SAc is overlaid with the Hermes DNA transposase (orange), showing high structural similarity. (2) Schematic of relative DDD/E and RW residue positions in hAT-6_XT transposases.

Figure S4: Coverage and divergence plots of the 8 horizontally transferred hAT-6_XT transposons. hAT-6_XT relative divergence and abundance were plotted using TE Aid (<https://github.com/clemgoub/TE-Aid>). The blue line represents the depth of coverage (right-hand Y-axis) of each fragment aligned to the repeat representative sequence. Green lines represent a full-length copy of the repeat. Black lines show repeat fragments. Percentage divergence from the representative sequence is shown on the left-hand Y-axis.

Concatenated_Mtt_hAT-6.blastnW7 vs. Concatenated_Tse_hAT-6.blastnW7
Zoom: 187 : 1
Word length: 10 GC ratio seq1: 0.4479
Window size: 0 GC ratio seq2: 0.4173
Matrix: DNA Program: Gepard (2.0)

Figure S5: Dot plot alignment of all the concatenated hAT-6_XT insertions (greater than 100 bp) in hAT-6_XT_MTT vs hAT-6_XT_TSE.

Concatenated_MTT... vs. Concatenated Chr...
Zoom: 845 : 1
Word length: 10 GC ratio seq1: 0.4479
Window size: 0 GC ratio seq2: 0.2681
Matrix: DNA Program: Gepard (2.0)

Figure S6: Dot plot alignment of all the concatenated hAT-6_XT insertions (greater than 100 bp) in hAT-6_XT_MTT vs hAT-6_XT_CPB.

Figure S7: Dot plot alignment of all the concatenated hAT-6_XT insertions (greater than 100 bp) in hAT-6_XT_MTT vs hAT-6_XT_DMa.

Concatenated_MTT_hAT-6.blastnW7 vs. Concatenated Malaclemmys terrapin pileata hAT-6
Zoom: 121 : 1
Word length: 10 GC ratio seq1: 0.4479
Window size: 0 GC ratio seq2: 0.4498
Matrix: DNA Program: Gepard (2.0)

Figure S8: Dot plot alignment of all the concatenated hAT-6_XT insertions (greater than 100 bp) in hAT-6_XT_MTT vs hAT-6_XT_MTP

Concatenated_Mtt_hAT-6.blastnW7 vs. Mesoclema tuberculata V0CS01023473.1:0-2361

Zoom: 217 : 1

Word length: 10

GC ratio seq1: 0.4479

Window size: 0

GC ratio seq2: 0.4422

Matrix: DNA

Program: Gepard (2.0)

Figure S9: Dot plot alignment of all the concatenated hAT-6_XT insertions (greater than 100 bp) in hAT-6_XT_MTT vs hAT-6_XT_MTu

Concatenated_MTT... vs. Concatenated ful...
Zoom: 615 : 1
Word length: 10 GC ratio seq1: 0.4479
Window size: 0 GC ratio seq2: 0.4451
Matrix: DNA Program: Gepard (2.0)

Figure S10: Dot plot alignment of all the concatenated hAT-6_XT insertions (greater than 100 bp) in hAT-6_XT_MTT vs hAT-6_XT_SOd

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hAT-6_XT_ESp TTCTAGACCACATGTGTCAAA-----/1860/
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp CAGTTGTTAAGACTGGAAAAG-----/23/
      * * * * *
hAT-6_XT_ESp atacagtggtgctcaaaagtttacatacacatgccttaagttgactaaaaagaggaat-aa
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp ctacagtggtgctcaaaagtttacatacacatgccttaagttgactaaaaagaggaataaa
      ***** **

hAT-6_XT_ESp aaaaatcatgttttggaatttattttaatacctaataaaaaatgaggtaaaatccaac
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp aaaaatcatgttttggaatttattttaatacctaataaaaaatgaggtaaaatccaac
      *****

hAT-6_XT_ESp cttaaggacaccaattttctttgtgaatgaataacgtattgtaataaataaatgttct
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp cttaaggacaccaattttctttgtgaatgaataacgtattgtaataaataaatgttct
      *****

hAT-6_XT_ESp tatttaaaatacaggggtcataagtatacataccctatgttaaatcccatagaggcag
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp tatttaaaatacaggggtcataagtatacataccctatgttaaatcccatagaggcag
      *****

hAT-6_XT_ESp gcagatttttattattaaggccagttatttctggattcaggatattatgcatcctgat
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp gcagatttttattattaaggacagttatttctggattcaggatattatgcatcctgat
      *****

hAT-6_XT_ESp aaagttccctggcctttagaatataaaatagccccacatcctcacatactttcacatg
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp aaagttccctggcctttagaatataaaatagccccacatcctcacatactttcacatg
      *****

hAT-6_XT_ESp cttagagataggcatggttttatttcagtttagactaataacctggtttgattgcattgag
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp cttagagataggcatggttttatttcagtttagactaataacctggtttgattgcattgag
      *****

hAT-6_XT_ESp agatgattttatagaaagtatcccatgcctatctcctaagcatgggtaagagatgtgagg
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp agatgattttatagaaagtatcccatgcctatctcctaagcatgggtaagagatgtgagg
      *****

hAT-6_XT_ESp atgtggggctattttaattctaaaggccaaggaactttatcaggatgcataatcctg
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp atgtggggctattttaattctaaaggccaaggaactttatcaggatgcataatcctg
      *****

hAT-6_XT_ESp aatccaggaataactggcctttaataataaaaaatctgcctgcctctatgggaatttaac
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp aatccaggaataactggcctttaataataaaaaatctgcctgcctctatgggaatttaac
      *****

hAT-6_XT_ESp atagggtatgtatacttatgacccctgtattttaaataagaacatttatttttaca
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp atagggtatgtatacttatgacccctgtattttaaataagaacatttatttttaca
      *****

hAT-6_XT_ESp tacgttattcattcacaagaaaattgggtgccttaaggttgattttacctcattttt
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp tacgttattcattcacaagaaaattgggtgccttaaggttgattttacctcattttt
      *****

hAT-6_XT_ESp taatttaggtattaaaataaatttccaaaacatga-tttttattcctctttttagtcaa
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp taatttaggtattaaaataaatttccaaaacatgattttttattcctctttttagtcaa
      *****

hAT-6_XT_ESp cttaaagcatgtgtatgtaaaacttttgaccactgtatgtgtcggagcagctgttctct
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp cttaaagcatgtgtatgtaaaacttttgaccactgtatat-----
      ***** *-----

hAT-6_XT_ESp /2679/-----AGTTTGACACCCCTGTTCTA
hAT-6N1_XT_ESp /1001/-----CTTTTGACAGTCTTAATGTA
      ***** ** * **

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Figure S11: Multiple alignment of *Etheostoma spectabile* (ESp) hAT-6_XT (blue) and hAT-6N1_XT_ESp (green). Shown in bold, terminally inverted repeats (TIRs) of hAT-6_XT_ESp show homology to TIRs of hAT-6N1_XT_ESp. Conserved residues are marked by asterisk (*).

Figure S12: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT derived non-autonomous DNA transposon compared (hAT-6N1_XT_ESp) to hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Etheostoma spectabile* (hAT-6_XT_ESp). The left-hand axis indicates the percentage of each TE in the genome and the bottom axis displays the relative age increasing from left to right.

Figure S13: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Etheostoma spectabile*. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

Figure S14: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Sygnathus acus*. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

Figure S15: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Scophthalmus maximus*. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

Figure S16: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Trachemys scripta elegans*. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

Figure S17: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Malaclemys terrapin*. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

Figure S18: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Scleropages formosus*. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

Figure S19: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Thalassophryne amazonica*. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

Figure S20: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Xenopus tropicalis*. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

Figure S21: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Dermatemys mawii*. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

Figure S22: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Chrysemys picta bellii*. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

Figure S23: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Malaclemys terrapin pileata*. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

Figure S24: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Mesoclemmys tuberculata*. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

Figure S25: Kimura distance-based divergence of hAT-6_XT from the genome of *Sternotherus odoratus*. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

(1) *Malaclemys terrapin terrapin* 🐢

(2) *Trachemys scripta elegans* 🐢

Figure S26: Kimura distance-based divergence of DNA transposons and retrotransposons from (1) *M.t. terrapin* and (2) *T.s. elegans*. DNA transposon (hAT-6_MTT/TSE, hAT-3_MTT/TSE, Mariner-1_MTT/TSE, and Harbinger-1_MTT/TSE) divergence is shown in contrast to the divergence of retrotransposons (Neptune-1_MTT/TSE and CR1-10_MTT/TSE) for both genomes. The left-hand axis for main plots and insets indicates base-pair counts of hAT-6_XT in the genome and the bottom axis for main plots and insets displays relative age shown from left to right.

Figure S27: Divergence plots for hAT-6_XT-like sequences from snake genomes. Length of sequence (bp) is shown on the X-axis. Jukes-Cantor distance is shown in the Y axis.

TE: CPB
consensus size: 1299bp; fragments: 200; full length: 0 ($\geq 90\%$)

Figure S28: Coverage and divergence plots of hAT-6_XT in *C.p. bellii*. hAT-6_XT relative divergence and abundance were plotted using TE Aid (<https://github.com/clemgoub/TE-Aid>) [47]. The blue line represents the depth of coverage (right-hand Y-axis) of each fragment aligned to the repeat representative sequence. Green lines represent a full-length copy of the repeat. Black lines show repeat fragments. Percentage divergence from the representative sequence is shown on the left-hand Y-axis.